

A NOVEL APPROACH FOR FUSION OF LOW RESOLUTION MULTISPECTRAL IMAGES IN REMOTE SENSING

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Abstract:

Nonlinear decomposition methods comprise a choice to conventional approaches for facing the problem of data fusion. In this paper, we discuss the application of this methodology to a admired remote sensing area called pan sharpening, which consists in the fusion of a low resolution multispectral image and a high-resolution panchromatic image. We design a complete pan sharpening scheme based on the use of morphological half gradient operators and demonstrate the application of this algorithm through the comparison with the state-of-the-art approaches. Four data sets obtained by the different satellites are employed for the performance monitoring, testifying the effectiveness of the proposed method in producing top-class images with a setting independent of the specific sensor.

Index Terms: Image Enhancement, Morphological Operators, Multispectral Imaging, Image Fusion & Remote Sensing

Introduction:

It is well known that combining several images of the same scene, characterized by different conditions of acquisition, allows to access a more precise description of the imaged objects by overcoming the intrinsic limitations of each modality considered separately [6]. A key example attracting a large interest in recent years is the *pan sharpening*, which refers to the generation of synthetic high resolution multichannel satellite images characterized by both a high spatial resolution and spectral diversity. The products of pan sharpening find a wide-spread use in platforms such as Google Earth and Microsoft Bing, as long as base data for scientific studies [7], [8]. Two sensors acquiring a multispectral (MS) image with low spatial resolution and a PAN chromatic (PAN) image with high spatial resolution are often available on board of the same satellite platform (e.g., Quickbird, Ikonos, SPOT, Landsat) producing simultaneous acquisitions that enjoy the favorable condition of being registered. Within data fusion problems, pan sharpening shows some specific characteristics, as for example, the different spatial resolutions of the available images and the need to preserve the characteristics of the MS data. These peculiarities have caused the development of a vast dedicated scientific literature [8], composed by both classical and novel approaches. Classical approaches are in general based on relatively simple fusion schemes and are characterized by a low computational complexity [8]. Some recently proposed techniques depart from the classical architectures, such as those based on sparse representation theory [9]–[11], Bayesian inference [12], or variational methods [13]. However, although some of these latter approaches have shown promising results, they are still unpractical in operational scenarios due to their significant computational burden [14]. For this reason, the practical interest is still focused on classical approaches that have been well studied and assessed [8], [15]. A classical pan sharpening algorithm is articulated in two successive steps: i) the extraction of the spatial details from the PAN image (that are not resolved in the MS) obtained by subtracting to the PAN a low spatial resolution version of it, and ii) the injection of the extracted details in the available MS image. *Component Substitution (CS)* methods generate a low resolution PAN image from a linear combination of the available MS channels. with the substitution of a component in a transformed domain, as, for example, in the space generated through the *IHS (Intensity-Hue-Saturation)* transformation, the *Principal Component Analysis (PCA)* and the *Gram-Schmidt (GS)* orthogonalization procedure. The CS methods produce visually appealing images and are widely used for their computational efficiency and their robustness to misregistration and aliasing errors [16]. In linear pyramids the analysis operator is implemented through the convolution of the image with a low pass mask. However their spectral accuracy is often low and tends to get worse with the increase of channels [8]. An alternative technique for extracting the details is provided by the *MultiResolution Analysis (MRA)* of the PAN image, which is generally obtained by linear decomposition methods, such as those based on wavelet [17],

A. Basics of Morphological Operators: Morphological operators act by probing a scalar image $I : E \subseteq Z^2 \rightarrow V \subseteq Z$ through a set called *Structuring Element (SE)* B [2]. The SE is defined by its spatial support $N_B(x)$ that is the neighborhood with respect to the position. A number of morphological operators can be obtained by combining these four elementary bricks (see for example [1], [2]). In the following we focus on the operators aimed to extract the image details, or equivalently, on their

complementary operators that reduce the resolution, thus representing possible candidates for the MRA analysis steps. The *internal gradient* $\rho^- [I] = I - \varepsilon_B [I]$ and the *external gradient* $\rho^+ [I] = \delta_B [I] - I$ are the residuals of the application of erosion and dilation. Analogously, the top-hat transforms are the complementary operators of opening and closing, hence showing the residuals of the filtering:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{WTH}_B [I] &= I - \gamma_B [I], \\ \text{BTH}_B [I] &= \varphi_B [I] - [I], \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

The result of a TC mapping is obtained by selectively toggling between the result of a dilation or erosion according to the result which is closest to the original image. TC mapping has been useful for image sharpening [2].

B. Some Existing Nonlinear Analysis Operators: Nonlinear multiresolution schemes constitute a wide class of signal decompositions [21]–[23] that allow for an accurate extraction of the details from an image, which is a fundamental aspect of pan sharpening. The crucial choice for their Morphological decomposition schemes were firstly proposed in [40], exploiting the use of a morphological filter, i.e., an idempotent and increasing operator [1]. In particular, the analysis operator was constituted by the sequence of an opening and closing (CO), namely it was defined as:

$$\psi_{\text{CO}, B} = \varphi_B \gamma_B. \quad (12)$$

Similarly to many other elementary morphological operators, $\psi_{\text{CO}, B}$ introduces a bias on the image values [32]–[34], i.e., the mean value of the filtered image is not preserved with respect to the original image. This constitutes a critical aspect for pan sharpening application, since it can prejudice the quality of the final product. A solution to this problem consists in combining multiple operators in order to reduce the shift effect [41]. Taking advantage of the opposite bias entailed by the two morphological filters $\varphi_B \gamma_B$ and $\gamma_B \varphi_B$ [34], the *Linear Combination of OC and CO* (LOCO) operator defined as

$$\psi_{\text{LC}, B} = 0.5(\varphi_B \gamma_B + \gamma_B \varphi_B) \quad (13)$$

was proposed in [41] and there used for denoising applications. The same rationale motivated the choice of Flouzat [42] and Laporterie-Déjean et al. [43], which employed the semi-sum of opening and closing

Thus, the analysis operator, that we indicate with the subscript *TT*, assumed the expression

$$\psi_{\text{TT}, B} = id - 0.5[(\text{WTH}_B - \text{BTH}_B) - (\text{DTC}_B - \text{ETC}_B)],$$

(16) in which, for the same reason, we added again the factor 0.5 with respect to the original definition. Finally we report a different example of nonlinear decomposition scheme. The *Multiscale Median Transform* (MMT) is a very simple instance proposed in [45] for astronomical applications. The analysis operator is defined as scheme. In particular Bai et al. [44] constructed a detail extraction operator as the difference of the Dilation Toggle Contrast operators $\text{DTC}_B = \max(\text{TC}_B - id, 0)$ and the Erosion Toggle Contrast operators $\text{ETC}_B = \max(id - \text{TC}_B, 0)$, namely the analysis operator was defined according to the formula:

$$\begin{aligned} \psi_{\text{TC}, B} &= id - \psi_{\text{TC}} = id - 0.5[\text{DTC}_B - \text{ETC}_B] \\ &= id - 0.5[\max(\text{TC}_B - id, 0) - \max(id - \text{TC}_B)] \end{aligned}$$

C. Analysis Operator Based on Half-Gradients: In this work we propose to use of the half gradients for detail extraction. Fig. 2(b) and Fig. 2(c) illustrate the effect of the internal and external gradients with a flat SE B with neighborhood $N_B = \{-1, 0, 1\}$ on the piecewise-constant mono-dimensional signal f depicted in Fig. 2(a). In the presence of discontinuities both half-gradients assume positive values that constitutes an approximation of the norm of the signal gradient [2]. The positive values of the internal gradient $\rho^- [f]$ follow

the positive discontinuities and precede the negative ones, while those of $\rho^+ [f]$ experience the opposite behavior. As a result, the difference of the two gradients represents a suitable detail extraction operator $\psi_{HG, B}$, since it reproduces the variations of the function with respect to the local mean. In particular we use the following definition

$$\psi_{HG, B} = 0.5(\rho^- - \rho^+) = 0.5(id - B) - 0.5(\delta B - id),$$

Where the low pass version of the PAN image acts as the background luminance. Therefore the application of $\psi_{HG, B}$ corresponds to estimate the background luminance as the midrange values within a neighborhood set by the SE B . This approach has been already employed in [46] and is particularly advisable when small neighborhoods are considered. Indeed the midrange is a very efficient and robust estimator of the location parameter of *platykurtic* (with broad curvature) distributions [47], [48]. The latter are characterized by a small value (≤ 2.2) of the normalized fourth central moment of the distribution,

D. Effect of the Detail Extraction Operators: A Toy Example: With the aim of illustrating the main features of the different definitions, we report in Fig. 2 the results of applying the operators described in Sect. III-B and the proposed method presented in Sect. III-C to the one dimensional signal depicted in Fig. 2(a). On the left column plots the effect of the analysis operators ψ is drawn with red dash lines together with the original signal f (in solid blue lines); on the right column the plots report the output of the details extraction operators $\psi = id - \psi$ (solid red lines). We implement all the morphological operators by employing a flat SE with neighborhood $N_B = \{-1, 0, 1\}$ that is also used for computing the output of the median filter. The

test signal has been designed to present both a fast dynamic (first half of its domain) and slower variations (second half). In the second part the function discontinuities are spaced by intervals of constant values with length greater than the support of the SE B . The comparison of the operators' behavior over the whole domain evidences that in general ψ_{HG} is able to extract the most significant amount of details. We underline that this is a very important feature for image fusion since smaller details in the PAN might appear as intensity variations with a spatial support of few pixels. Remarkably, all the discontinuities of the test signal are detected by the proposed operator. Moreover, the amplitude of signal variations is correctly extracted by the operator allowing the preservation of the dynamic of the signal. We will see in the following that in pan sharpening this is a necessary feature to limit spectral distortions in the results. Among the other operators, the TC defined by (15) is less sensitive to the local signal variations, being zero almost everywhere. On the contrary, ψ_{LC} and ψ_{TH} (and the very similar ψ_{TT}) are able to reproduce the details with sufficient accuracy, but only in the first half of the observation interval, where the signal varies over intervals smaller than the SE length. In fact, in the second half of the signal support only ψ_{HG} is able to detect the signal variation, while the output of the others is identically null.

Experimental Results:

In this section we compare the behavior of the different analyzed algorithms on real images. Due to the unavailability of the target HRMS image, the assessment of pan sharpening algorithms is typically performed with two companion protocols [8]. The reduced resolution assessment involves the degradation of both the original MS and PAN images. This procedure has to be completed according to the Wald protocol [50], namely the MS image has to be degraded by filtering through a system mimicking the response of the sensors and by decimating by a factor equal to the resolution ratio r . We employed a Gaussian filter with the same gain at the Nyquist frequency of the specific sensor for the MS images and an almost ideal filter for the PAN image [51]. This methodology allows the exploitation of a wide range of quality indexes, since the original MS image acts as the target image for the fusion process. We selected the *Spectral Angle Mapper (SAM)* [52] as a measure of the spectral quality and two comprehensive indexes, the $Q2^n$ -index [53], [54], and the *Erreur Relative Globale Adimensionnelle de Synthèse (ERGAS)* [55] for evaluating both spatial and spectral quality. Optimal values are 0 for the SAM and the ERGAS and 1 for the $Q2^n$. On the other hand, the reduced resolution assessment is based on the scale invariance assumption that cannot be undoubtedly assumed in the real practice. For that reason it has to be supplemented by the full resolution assessment that employs the available images at the original resolution. Since the target HRMS image does not exist at that level, indexes with no reference have to be employed. In this work we separately assess the spectral and spatial quality of the pan sharpened image, by employing the *SAM index* for the former and the *Spatial Correlation Coefficient (SCC)* [56] for the latter. The optimal value of the SCC index is 1. The employed data sets are described in the first subsection, while the performance assessment of the algorithms are reported in the following subsections. We firstly compare the different analysis operators that are eligible for implementing the morphological pyramid decomposition and then evaluate the chosen scheme together with some of the most credited algorithms present in the literature.

Conclusion:

In this work we studied the application of nonlinear image decomposition schemes based on morphological operators to data fusion, and in particular to the problem of pan sharpening. Although the properties of morphology-based methods are widely exploited for applications as segmentation and denoising, only a limited number of data fusion approaches have taken advantage by their ability in dealing with shapes. The effective application of MM to pan sharpening requires the choice of a suitable spatial detail extraction operator that we designed as the difference of the two half-gradients. We evidenced that it allows to highlight all the spatial changes of the input image, preserving the dynamics of the signal variation and a local zero mean value, as required by pan-sharpening applications. A comprehensive fusion architecture, encompassing the choice of the MRA implementation options and of the detail injection method, was here proposed and evaluated. Four data sets acquired by four different sensors were used for the algorithm assessment, using both the reduced and full resolution quality evaluation protocols. The results show that the proposed method greatly outclasses the existing pan sharpening algorithms based on mathematical morphology. Actually it achieves top-class performance, aligned with that of best pan sharpening algorithms, without requiring specific knowledge of the used sensor, as for example the MTF shape. As possible future developments, we plan to consider other tools provided by mathematical morphology that can be suitable in data fusion problems, as for example the levelings operators.

References:

1. J. Serra, *Image Analysis and Mathematical Morphology*. New York, NY, USA: Academic, 1984.
2. P. Soille, *Morphological Image Analysis: Principles and Applications*. Berlin, Germany: Springer-Verlag, 2003.
3. Toet, "Hierarchical image fusion," *Mach. Vis. Appl.*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 1–11, Dec. 1990.

4. S. Mukhopadhyay and B. Chanda, "Fusion of 2D grayscale images using multiscale morphology," *Pattern Recognit.*, vol. 34, no. 10, pp. 1939–1949, Oct. 2001.
5. X. Bai, "Morphological image fusion using the extracted image regions and details based on multi-scale top-hat transform and toggle contrastoperator," *Digit. Signal Process.* vol. 23, no. 2, pp. 542–554, Mar. 2013.
6. M. DallaMura, S. Prasad, F. Pacifici, P. Gamba, J. Chanussot, and J. A. Benediktsson, "Challenges and opportunities of multimodality and data fusion in remote sensing," *Proc. IEEE*, vol. 103, no. 9, pp. 1585–1601, Sep. 2015.